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Fully automatic segmentation and monitoring of choriocapillaris flow voids in OCTA images

Emilio López-Varela^{a,b}, Joaquim de Moura^{a,b,*}, Jorge Novo^{a,b}, José Ignacio Fernández-Vigo^{c,d}, Francisco Javier Moreno-Morillo^c, Marcos Ortega^{a,b}

^a VARPA Group, Biomedical Research Institute of A Coruña (INIBIC), University of A Coruña, A Coruña, Spain

^b CITIC-Research Center of Information and Communication Technologies, University of A Coruña, A Coruña, Spain

^c Departamento de Oftalmología, Hospital Clínico San Carlos, Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria (IdISSC), Madrid, Spain

^d Centro Internacional de Oftalmología Avanzada, Madrid, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) is a non-invasive ophthalmic imaging modality that is widely used in clinical practice. Recent technological advances in OCTA allow imaging of blood flow deeper than the retinal layers, at the level of the choriocapillaris (CC), where a granular image is obtained showing a pattern of bright areas, representing blood flow, and a pattern of small dark regions, called flow voids (FVs). Several clinical studies have reported a close correlation between abnormal FVs distribution and multiple diseases, so quantifying changes in FVs distribution in CC has become an area of interest for many clinicians. However, CC OCTA images present very complex features that make it difficult to correctly compare FVs during the monitoring of a patient. In this work, we propose fully automatic approaches for the segmentation and monitoring of FVs in CC OCTA images. First, a baseline approach, in which a fully automatic segmentation methodology based on local contrast enhancement and global thresholding is proposed to segment FVs and measure changes in their distribution in a straightforward manner. Second, a robust approach in which, prior to the use of our segmentation methodology, an unsupervised trained neural network is used to perform a deformable registration that aligns inconsistencies between images acquired at different time instants. The proposed approaches were tested with CC OCTA images collected during a clinical study on the response to photodynamic therapy in patients affected by chronic central serous chorioretinopathy (CSC), demonstrating their clinical utility. The results showed that both approaches are accurate and robust, surpassing the state of the art, therefore improving the efficacy of FVs as a biomarker to monitor the patient treatments. This gives great potential for the clinical use of our methods, with the possibility of extending their use to other pathologies or treatments associated with this type of imaging.

1. Introduction

Computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems have gained popularity over the recent years as auxiliary tools to support the clinical evaluation of different diseases, significantly increasing the robustness of diagnostic procedures. This technology can be applied to different imaging modalities, such as optical coherence tomography (OCT) (Díaz et al., 2019b, 2019a; Eladawi et al., 2018; López-Varela et al., 2022c, 2022a) or optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) (Samagaio et al., 2018; Vidal et al., 2018; López-Varela et al., 2022b; Baamonde et al.,

2019). In particular, OCTA is an imaging modality used in ophthalmology that is increasing its popularity and use in the clinical setting as it facilitates the diagnosis and monitoring of various ocular and systemic diseases. OCTA is a non-invasive imaging modality that is characterized by its capability to show a detailed visualization of the retinal vascularity (De Carlo et al., 2015; Jia et al., 2012). To acquire the images, the OCTA devices use the variation in signal intensity of the OCT scans over time as a contrast mechanism to obtain OCTA images (Wang et al., 2007; Fingler et al., 2007). Recent advances in OCTA devices allow the imaging of the blood flow deeper than the retinal layers, at the level of the

* Corresponding author at: VARPA Group, Biomedical Research Institute of A Coruña (INIBIC), University of A Coruña, A Coruña, Spain.

E-mail addresses: e.lopezv@udc.es (E. López-Varela), joaquim.demoura@udc.es (J. de Moura), jnovo@udc.es (J. Novo), jfvigo@hotmail.com (J.I. Fernández-Vigo), javimorenomorillo@gmail.com (F.J. Moreno-Morillo), mortega@udc.es (M. Ortega).

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Fig. 1. Representative examples of CC OCTA images showing a pattern of bright areas, representing the presence of blood flow, and a pattern of small dark regions representing the absence of blood flow, called flow voids. The deepness of the slab is 29–49 μm . At the top of each image its corresponding structural OCT is shown where the green area shows the choroid and the yellow line marks the segmentation of the choriocapillaris.

choriocapillaris (CC), providing new dynamic information about choroidal physiology. OCTA is currently the only non-invasive modality available for CC imaging in a clinical setting. Also, CC flow is not adequately visualized by traditional angiography, making OCTA the only usable alternative. When OCTA is used to image the choroidal innermost thickness, a granular image is obtained (Spaide et al., 2015) showing a pattern of bright areas, representing blood flow, and a pattern of small dark regions showing areas without blood flow called flow voids (FVs) as shown in Fig. 1.

Several clinical studies (Cao et al., 1998; Luty et al., 1999; Bhatta and Luty, 2012) have reported a close correlation between abnormal distribution of FVs and multiple retinal and choroidal diseases, such as age-related macular degeneration, diabetic retinopathy or glaucoma. Consequently, the visualization and quantification of the changes in the FVs characteristics in normal and diseased eyes has become an area of interest for many researchers, as there is the potential to use changes in this distribution as a relevant biomarker for the diagnosis and monitoring of the progression of certain pathologies (Ho et al., 2020; Chu et al., 2018; Al-Sheikh et al., 2017b; Spaide, 2016a; Pepple et al., 2018). In addition, it can also be used to monitor the effectiveness of a treatment that is applied, for example, in the treatment of central serous chorioretinopathy (CSC), an ocular disease that is among the leading causes of visual acuity (VA) impairment in patients under 60 years of age. Currently, one of the preferred treatments for chronic CSC is photodynamic therapy, which has been shown to be useful in improving or stabilizing VA. Photodynamic therapy is a treatment that involves a

light-sensitive medicine and a light source to destroy abnormal cells. The main problem with this treatment is that the efficacy of the treatment is highly variable between patients, for what having a method that allows an accurate and repeatable monitoring is of vital importance. In daily clinical practice, the analysis of FVs on CC OCTA images is done by careful visual inspection by an clinical expert, a process that is extremely tedious and time-consuming. For this reason, a fully automated system for the quantification of FVs using CC OCTA imaging is significantly useful, as it would facilitate the work of the clinicians by increasing the robustness and accuracy of the diagnosis and would drastically reduce the workload and consequently the direct and indirect costs for the healthcare services (Ho et al., 2020; Fernández-Vigo et al., 2022).

Despite its great potential, an accurate analysis of the distribution of FVs is challenging due to the characteristics of the CC OCTA imaging modality. The CC lies beneath the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE), a layer that scatters a lot of light. In this sense, various anomalies in the RPE/Bruch's membrane (BM) complex, such as drusen and other detachments from the RPE, would lead to signal attenuation and uneven illumination of the CC, which can produce artificial shadows not caused by tissue hypofusion that could be misinterpreted as FVs. One potential source of this type of artifact is the presence of subretinal fluid (SRF), a fluid that is commonly present in various ocular diseases such as CSC. Usually its composition is very rich in proteins, which causes an increase in absorption and thus signal attenuation in the layers below it. The effect this has on the final OCTA image can be reduced in several ways, although never completely eliminated. One of the most effective ways to

reduce this signal attenuation is the use of devices using swept source OCT (SS-OCT) technology, which minimizes this effect to some extent compared to older technologies such as spectral domain OCT (SD-OCT). The use of this technology provides good repeatability with respect to other SD-OCT devices for quantifying macular flow voids, even when subretinal fluid is present (Reich et al., 2020). In addition, CC OCTA images are characterized by a very rough and grainy appearance, presenting numerous and complex local deformations and, unlike other imaging modalities such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), do not present clear and defined anatomical structures. This landmark scarcity together with the complex texture that is present in this type of images, makes it drastically difficult to perform an accurate and robust quantification of the FVs distribution. This is especially relevant when monitoring a pathology or the efficacy of a treatment, where images of the same patient are taken at separate time intervals. These images show numerous differences between them due to local deformations, which makes it very difficult to compare the distribution of the FVs among them.

Given the novelty and complex characteristics of this imaging modality, there are currently only a few studies that partially address the segmentation and quantification of FVs in CC OCTA imaging. In most cases, due to the novelty of this imaging modality, these are proposals presenting semi-automated systems, simple methods that are normally auxiliary to clinical studies or adaptations of previously developed methodologies to solve similar problems without taking into account the specific challenges of this domain. Moreover, these methods are not

intended for patient monitoring, as they do not take into account the profound changes that CC OCTA images obtained at different time intervals undergo. As reference, Sugano et al. (2018) used a semi-automated system, called AngioTool (Zudaire et al., 2011), to perform a morphometric analysis of the choriocapillaris using OCTA images. AngioTool was validated using images of embryonic murine hindbrains, post-natal retinas and allantois explants. In the work of Al-Sheikh et al. (2017a), the authors proposed the use of the greyscale values as a measure of FVs in healthy subjects with CC OCTA images. For this purpose, the authors used the classical Otsu global threshold method, obtaining partitions of the grayscale histogram into two classes. The histogram of CC OCTA images does not follow a bimodal distribution so the use of this method is very limited, mainly in the pathological cases. Alten et al. (2016) proposed a clinical study on the behaviour of blood flow under reticular pseudodrusen using OCTA imaging. In this sense, the authors using the mean pixel value in the outer retinal layer as a reference to establish a global threshold. Last, the Phansalkar local thresholding method (Phansalkar et al., 2011) is the standard method commonly used in ophthalmic research studies related to FVs quantification (Rochepeau et al., 2018; Spaide, 2016b; Yang et al., 2020; Nassisi et al., 2019). Phansalkar first introduced this local thresholding technique to segment cell nuclei in cytologic and histologic images. This local approximation is more robust to illumination changes in the image than a simple global perspective, but it can overestimate the amount of FVs in the image by labeling as FVs pixels that are not FVs pixels in local areas with high values. In addition, most of the contributions in the

Fig. 2. Representative examples of CC OCTA images obtained from six patients diagnosed with chronic CSC. For each patient the image before and after application of photodynamic therapy is shown.

clinical setting use size filters which can affect the repeatability of the method by altering the FVs/noise ratio between different images. Furthermore, this method was designed for use with histological imaging, so its use in CC OCTA imaging is not as optimized as a method specifically designed for this type of imaging.

On the other hand, an important limitation of the above methods is the use of a single time instant to quantify the distribution of FVs over time. When using the FVs distribution as a biomarker to follow the progression of a disease or to monitor/predict the efficacy of a treatment, images obtained from the same patient at different time intervals are used. Therefore, the methodologies proposed in the state of the art are affected by the deformations produced in the time sequence, which limits their capacity to quantify the FVs adequately. The potential correction of these deformations, in order to match the noise and keep only those FVs that are significant, can lead to a better comparison of the distribution of FVs over time increasing the efficiency of the extracted biomarkers and also allowing pixel-to-pixel comparisons between diagnostic images obtained throughout the treatment. However, the correction of these deformations is challenging, due to the landmark scarcity and the dominant granular texture that characterizes CC OCTA images. For this reason, it is essential to develop a robust and accurate registration method that solves these deformations by confronting the problems that characterize this type of image modality.

Given the significant gap in the literature, and taking into account the potential of FVs as a biomarker, in this work we propose a novel methodology for the FVs segmentation in CC OCTA images, a new ophthalmic imaging modality with great diagnostic potential. For this purpose, we design a fully automatic strategy, based on the use of local contrast enhancement followed by a global thresholding strategy. This strategy was designed to deal with the characteristic drawbacks of this type of images, gaining robustness against the state of the art. Moreover, taking into account that these characteristics make patient monitoring more difficult in any pathology, we also propose an efficient and accurate deformable registration methodology, based on a convolutional neural network trained by unsupervised learning. This methodology allows us to correct the numerous inconsistencies that are present in CC OCTA images obtained at different time instants despite the landmark scarcity and the complex texture that characterizes this type of images. This allows the study of the FVs evolution to be more reliable and accurate, which greatly helps to study various pathologies over time, improving patient monitoring. To validate and analyse the proposed approaches, we conducted extensive experimentation with cases from a real clinical study of patients affected by CSC, designed specifically for this work.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the only work that presents a fully automatic methodology specifically dedicated to accurately quantifying changes in the distribution of FVs over time. Our segmentation methodology is robust and repeatable, which allows better monitoring of patients in the treatment of different eye diseases, as in our case with patients affected by chronic CSC.

This manuscript is organized as follows: “Section 2” presents all the resources needed to fully reproduce our work. “Section 3” presents a detailed explanation of the proposed approaches as well as the evaluation process. “Section 4” includes the results and their subsequent discussion, as well as the main challenges faced in this work. Finally, “Section 5” presents the general conclusions of the study and possible lines of future work.

2. Materials

In this section, we describe the CC OCTA dataset, as well as the software and hardware resources that were used in this work. Both resources are described in detail below.

2.1. Dataset

In this work, we use a dataset composed of CC OCTA images that were acquired during photodynamic therapy treatment of patients affected by chronic CSC. Specifically, these images were obtained from pathological and healthy contralateral eyes over different time instants corresponding to pre-treatment, 2–4 days after treatment, 1 month after treatment, 3 months after treatment, and 6 months after treatment. Obtaining these images during the whole treatment process allows us to study the validity of our methodology for the monitoring of a pathology. Moreover, changes in the distribution of FVs after photodynamic treatment are closely related to the long-term efficacy of this treatment, making images of patients suffering from this pathology very suitable for studying the.

efficacy of flow voids extraction methodologies. In Fig. 2, we can see representative examples of pre and post-treatment image pairs, where the effect of the photodynamic therapy is appreciated.

In particular, the dataset consists of a total of 821 CC OCTA images (1024×1024 pixels). These images were acquired from both eyes of 52 patients, so we have images from 104 eyes in total (being 52 healthy and 52 pathological eyes).

All the patients were followed-up 2–3 days, 1, 3 and 6 months after treatment. This dataset was specifically designed for this study and was obtained with the Zeiss Plex Elite capture device, using a central wavelength between 1040 nm and 1060 nm with an axial resolution of 6,3 μm , a transverse resolution of 20 μm and a scanning speed of 100,000 A-scans per second. This device uses SS-OCT technology which has proven to be much more effective than traditional SD-OCT technology in imaging the layers beneath the retina by reducing signal attenuation in these layers. Only images of sufficient quality, as determined by a signal quality > 7 , were accepted. In addition, a 6×6 mm scan centered in the macula was performed and based on the default settings of the OCTA software device, the CC slab extends 29–49 μm below the RPE layer. The projection elimination algorithm of the device software was applied to all the images in order to eliminate false positives caused by deformations of the upper retinal layers. In addition, regarding the criteria for inclusion and exclusion of patients:

- **Inclusion criteria:** Persistent CSC with persistent SRF at or near the fovea ($< 500 \mu\text{m}$) for at least 3 months without any previous treatments in the last 6 months. Patients had to be susceptible to undergo a standardized PDT with a spot laser size of $4000 \pm 500 \mu\text{m}$.
- **Exclusion criteria:** Previous eye surgery, another maculopathy, active treatment with steroids, pregnancy, poor image quality due to motion artefacts or abundant vitreous floaters, and the presence of choroidal neovascularization.

The patients underwent a complete ophthalmologic examination including best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) using the Early Treatment Diabetic Retinopathy Study (ETDRS) scale, slit lamp biomicroscopy and posterior segment ophthalmoscopy. The age, gender and axial length (AL) (IOL master 700; Carl Zeiss Jena, Germany) were also recorded. The age of the patients enrolled in the study ranged from 30 to 60 years. 31 of the 52 patients were men and 21 were women. All explorations were performed within the same time frame (between 9:00 am and 14:00 pm) to avoid diurnal variations of the choroidal structures. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant and the study protocol adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Clínico San Carlos. All CC OCTA images were taken by two well-trained examiners and each patient is labeled in a binary manner (recovered, not recovered) based on the efficacy of the photodynamic therapy applied. This efficacy is based on several factors involving the patient recovery over the next 3 months with the main factor being the reabsorption of persistent subretinal fluid. In this regard, our dataset presents considerable variability. On the one hand, we have patients in whom the

Table 1
Specifications of the equipment that was used during this work.

Name	Description
OS	Ubuntu 20.04.1 LTS (Focal Fossa)
Kernel	Linux 5.4.0-81-generic
Architecture	x86-64
CPU	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2650 v4 @ 2.20 GHz
GPU	NVIDIA Corporation Tesla M60
Driver Version	430.99
CUDA Version	10.1

Fig. 3. Diagram of the segmentation methodology proposed.

amount of fluid is reduced after treatment. On the other hand, we have patients in whom the amount of fluid does not change. And finally, we even have patients who get worse after treatment. This variability in the dataset allows us to test our method robustly in all these different types of cases.

2.2. Software and hardware resources

Regarding the software resources, we used Python 3.7.9 with PyTorch 1.6 (Paszke et al., 2019) and the OpenCV 4.5.1.48 (Itseez, 2015) for the implementation of the proposed approaches. In addition, we used the ImageJ software (Schindelin et al., 2012) to reproduce the Phansalkar (Phansalkar et al., 2011) state of the art method, the most widely used method in clinical studies for FVs segmentation in OCTA images (although it was designed to segment cell nuclei in cytological and histological images). Regarding hardware resources, we include in Table 1 the full disclosure of the components, drivers and software that have been used throughout the development of this work and that may have influenced its computational performance.

3. Methodology

Full details of the proposed segmentation approaches are presented below. On one hand, in Section 3.1 we present the general segmentation methodology, where the FVs of each single image are segmented, resulting in a binary segmentation mask. On the other hand, in Section 3.2 two approaches are presented to carry out the study of the evolution

of the FVs during patient monitoring. Specifically, in this work our proposals are applied to monitor photodynamic therapy treatment of patients with CSC, a pathology extremely correlated with FVs distribution. First, a baseline proposal is presented that quantifies the differences in FVs over time in a straightforward manner. Then, an improved proposal is presented, where using our registration methodology the differences between the images due to local deformations are corrected. This allows us to achieve a better alignment between the images before quantifying the FVs differences, making the quantification more robust.

3.1. Fully automatic FVs image segmentation

The proposed segmentation methodology is based on increasing the contrast of the image locally and, then, applying a global thresholding, given its simplicity, computational performance and adequate results for many relevant image segmentation issues (Setiawan et al., 2013; Saifullah and Suryotomo, 2021; Gupta et al., 2021). A diagram of this segmentation methodology is shown in Fig. 3. Complementarily, a representative example of the segmentation process is shown in Fig. 4, where we can see the results of each step of the proposed methodology.

- First, the CC OCTA images were normalized to a common range of values using a min-max normalization. The obtained values were mapped to the common range (0–255) using linear scaling.
- Then, a contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) with a neighborhood size of 8×8 was applied. The value of the neighborhood size was chosen taking into account previous experiments. The application of CLAHE allows us to increase the contrast between the darkest and lightest areas of the image locally. This negates the problems caused by the illumination changes in small areas of the image and allows us to segment the FVs more accurately using a global thresholding strategy.
- Finally, an inverse global threshold was applied resulting in the binary image in which the FVs were marked in white. In this regard, knowing how easy it is to produce an overestimation of the number of FVs, we performed an exhaustive search to find the optimal threshold value. This was done in order to observe which value was able to decrease the noise level in the most optimal way (consistently across all images) while maintaining the actual level of the FVs present in the image.

3.2. Assessment of FVs changes in response to photodynamic therapy in chronic CSC

As mentioned above, to monitor a patient over the time, images of the same area are taken days or months apart. Different characteristics (such as the area of FVs in the image) can be used as representative biomarkers, so that their increase or decrease can indicate an improvement or worsening of the associated pathology. In our particular case, the long-term efficacy of photodynamic therapy treatment in

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the proposed segmentation approach.

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the methodology for the quantitative analysis of the evolution of the FVs changes.

patients with CSC can be estimated by observing the change in FVs distribution before and after treatment. In order to carry out this estimation, it is necessary to segment the FVs accurately and robustly, so that local deformations and noise that characterize these images, do not affect the quantification of this change. In addition, it should be taken into account that in some cases there is usually less subretinal fluid and thus less attenuation of the signal after treatment, which may produce a slight bias in the results obtained by any method. This signal attenuation should occur globally throughout the image and not at specific points. In our baseline segmentation methodology, the contrast of each OCTA image is adjusted, which allows us to accurately segment the flow voids regardless of how much the overall image signal is reduced or increased, reducing this potential bias. Two proposals for quantifying this change in FVs distribution are presented below. A baseline approach, in which the FVs are segmented and the change is measured directly, and another in which it is proposed to use a registration methodology to align the local deformations and noise between the images. This alignment allows us to segment the FVs in a more robust way, avoiding the natural deformations that are present between the two images, resulting in a much more accurate quantification of the change in the number of FVs.

3.3. Quantitative analysis of the evolution of the FVs changes

The baseline approach to analyze the evolution of the FVs consists of calculating the area occupied by the FVs in each image and measuring the percentage of change of this value. To calculate the area of FVs, we use our segmentation methodology (Section 3.1), with which we extract a binary mask of the FVs. We count the number of pixels that are FVs in the mask and once we get the area occupied by the FVs in the images before and after treatment, we calculate the percentage of change. A

schematic of this approach is shown in Fig. 5.

3.3.1. Robust quantitative analysis of the evolution of the FVs changes using unsupervised image deformable registration support

As previously mentioned, CC OCTA images are characterized by a very rough and grainy appearance. When monitoring a patient, this type of images are obtained over the weeks or months. This time interval between the acquisition of each image, combined with the characteristics explained above, means that CC OCTA images acquired in the same area have many local deformations. These complex and numerous local deformations greatly affect the analysis of changes in the number of FVs over the time, as they add noise and differences between images that are not really significant. Any methodology applied to these images on an individual level without taking these deformations into account is affected by these factors, reducing its repeatability, accuracy and limiting its usefulness. To mitigate all these drawbacks and improve the robustness and accuracy of our baseline approach, we present a deformable registration methodology, which is used as a preliminary step to our baseline approach. This deformable registration allows correcting local deformations, improving the alignment of the images, which allows capturing in a more accurate and robust way the evolution of the changes in the FVs over time. This improves the efficacy of the FVs as a biomarker, helping to monitor the patient more effectively. Fig. 6 shows a diagram of the proposed approach in which an unsupervised deformable registration strategy is used to align the CC OCTA images before performing FVs segmentation stage. This deformable registration is challenging to resolve due to the characteristics that the CC OCTA images typically present such as granularity and lack of clear and defined anatomical structures. To overcome this landmark scarcity, we developed a deformable registration through a powerful multiscale

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of the proposed methodology. We use a neural network with which we perform a deformable registration on the images obtained at different time instants, in this case pre and post-treatment. Then, our segmentation methodology is used.

neural network.

3.3.2. Network architecture

We designed a deformable register network architecture composed of different convolutional layers and a specific spatial transform. In particular, the network input consists of the CC OCTA image to be registered and the reference CC OCTA image. The network is divided into 3 branches that use the input images at different scales (high, medium and low resolution CC OCTA images). In each of these branches, convolutions are applied with kernels of size 3×3 and a stride of 2. Each convolution is followed by a batch normalization layer that helps the convergence of the model acting as a regulating factor (Horwath et al., 2020) and a LeakyReLU layer. The low resolution branch allows to make convolutions in a fast and efficient way, being able to accumulate several consecutive convolutions which increases the receptive field. In

order to further increase the receptive field, the last convolution of this branch is applied using a dilation.

This branch allows feature maps to be generated in an efficient way in which differences between images involving large deformations in pixel spacing are represented. This allows the independent medium and high resolution branches to concentrate on finding fine features without having to provide a complete representation of all features that define the differences between images. This results in fewer convolutions being necessary which reduces the number of model parameters that have to be optimized, reducing the risk of overfitting and aiding in convergence (Battiti, 1994). In addition, the concentration of these branches on finding fine features serves both to refine the correction of these large deformations and to correct smaller, more subtle deformations present in the images. The 3 branches are merged by transpose convolutions that refine the features that define the large deformations while adding more

Fig. 7. Overview of the neural architecture. The network is composed of 3 branches that accept different sizes of inputs formed by convolutional layers, an expansive part that ends with some extra convolutional layers and finally a spatial transform that outputs the registration image.

Table 2

Transformations applied to moving and fixed images in each batch. From each group only one transformation can be applied at a time.

Groups	Transformations
Group 1	Coarse Dropout
Group 2	Piecewise Affine, Elastic Transform
Group 3	Vertical Flip
Group 4	Horizontal Flip
Group 5	Shift Scale Rotate
Group 6	Random Rotate 90°
Group 7	Gaussian Blur, Median Blur, Blur, Motion Blur
Group 8	Brightness Contrast, CLAHE
Group 9	Multiplicative Noise, Image Compression, Gauss Noise

subtle deformation-defining features. To refine the final feature maps, several additional series of convolutions are used. The output of this plus the image to be registered serve as input to the spatial transformer that produces the final registered image. Fig. 7 shows an overview of the neural architecture that was designed for this task. In particular, this neural architecture was designed to overcome the main challenges of our domain.

3.3.3. Training details

Details concerning the training of the deformable registration network are shown below. The dataset was randomly divided into 3 subsets, specifically 65 % of CC OCTA images for training, 15 % for validation and the remaining 20 % for testing. All the subsets were independent from each other and all the images of a patient belonged to a single set. Network parameters were initialized using the He et al. (He et al., 2015) method. The local normalized cross-correlation function (Balakrishnan et al., 2018), a well known metric that is robust to intensity variations, was used as loss function.

The mathematical representation is shown in Eq. (1) where $\hat{F}(p)$ and $\hat{M}(\phi(p))$ denote local mean intensity images:

$$LNCC = \frac{(\sum_{p_i}(F(p_i) - \hat{F}(p))(M(\phi(p_i)) - \hat{M}(\phi(p))))^2}{(\sum_{p_i}(F(p_i) - \hat{F}(p)))(\sum_{p_i}(M(\phi(p_i)) - \hat{M}(\phi(p))))} \quad (1)$$

A batch size of 6 was used, as it gave the best results in previous tests. In addition, as optimizer, we used the stochastic gradient descent with an initial learning rate of 0.001. It used a dynamic learning rate that was reduced by a factor of 0.7 if the loss of validation did not fall after 40 epochs. Early stopping was performed based on the validation loss. An exhaustive online data augmentation process has also been applied to make the model more robust and avoid overfitting (Buslaev et al., 2020). Some transformations were grouped so that only one from the group could be applied at a time. Table 2 shows all the transformations applied to the images.

To evaluate the deformable registration, we employ different complementary statistics that are used in the state of the art to measure the performance of computational approaches for similar tasks. In particular, we consider: the mean squared error (MSE) (2) where m and n are the number of rows and columns in the cover image. The normalized root-mean-square deviation (NRMSE) (3) where y_i is the i^{th} observation of y and \hat{y} is the predicted y value given the model. The structural similarity index measure (SSIM) (Wang et al., 2004) (4) where C_1 and C_2 are two constant variables to stabilize the division with weak denominator. The Multi-Scale Structural Similarity (MSSIM) (Wang et al., 2003) (5) where the contrast comparison and the structure comparison are denoted as $C_j(x, y)$ and $S_j(x, y)$, respectively and the luminance comparison is denoted as $l_M(x, y)$. The visual information fidelity (VIF) (Sheikh and Bovik, 2006) (6), where we sum over the channels of interest, and $C^{\rightarrow N_j}$ represent N elements of the random field C_j that describes the coefficients from channel j , and so on.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (x_{ij} - y_{ij})^2 \quad (2)$$

$$NRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2}}{\max_{x,y_i} - \min_{x,y_i}} \quad (3)$$

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1) + (2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \quad (4)$$

$$MSSIM(x, y) = [l_M(x, y)]^{aM} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [C_j(x, y)]^{B_j} \cdot [S_j(x, y)]^{C_j} \quad (5)$$

$$VIF = \frac{\sum_{j \in \text{subbands}} I(\vec{C}^{N_j}; \vec{F}^{N_j} | S^{N_j})}{\sum_{j \in \text{subbands}} I(\vec{C}^{N_j}; \vec{E}^{N_j} | S^{N_j})} \quad (6)$$

3.4. Evaluation strategy

In general, to validate segmentation methodologies, the segmentation masks that are obtained by the proposed approaches are compared with a ground truth labeled by an expert. In our case, it is impossible to use this type of validation, because it is not feasible to have a ground truth, since it is not possible to define each pixel as a FVs or vascular zone in a precise way. Because of this, we have defined an alternative way to validate our approaches and compare them with the state of the art. To do so, we use a subset of our total dataset composed of 42 image pairs. This subset of images is used for testing purposes only. Each image pair is labeled as recovered or non-recovered patient and consists of one image obtained before laser treatment and one image obtained days after treatment.

To validate the robustness of the proposed approaches, we calculated

Table 3

Correlation coefficient between patient recovery and percent change in FVs area calculated using our baseline approach.

Threshold	28	20	15	10
Coefficient	0.4724	0.4798	0.4820	0.4850
p-value	0.008	0.006	0.003	0.001

for each pair of CC OCTA images the percentage of change in the area of FVs. This percentage functions as a biomarker to predict patient recovery, but its efficacy depends on the accuracy and robustness of the methodology used to obtain it. Thus, a more accurate and robust segmentation methodology will produce a better correlation between the value of this biomarker and the recovery or not of the patients, increasing the separation between these two classes. Therefore, to compare the proposed methodologies with the state of the art, we measured the correlation between the biomarker and the recovered and non-recovered classes using the point biserial correlation. So a better correlation indicates a more robust and accurate FVs extraction.

On the other hand, it is also important to check that the methodologies developed are robust and repeatable. For this purpose, we used a subset of 42 pairs of CC OCTA images, where the two images in each pair were obtained seconds apart. Then, we checked using Student's t-test that there are no significant differences in the number of FVs extracted between each pair of CC OCTA images.

4. Results and discussion

In this section, we cover all the results that were acquired throughout the evaluation of the two proposed approaches for the quantification of the evolution of the FVs changes. First, we show the results of our baseline approach, where we also show the effect of selecting the optimal threshold value for our segmentation methodology. Second, we show the results that were obtained using our robust approach, where we use our deformable registration network to correct the differences and noise present in the images. Finally, we compare the results obtained using our methodologies with the state of the art.

4.1. Quantitative analysis of the evolution of the FVs changes: baseline approach

The results obtained using our baseline approach are shown below. As specified in Section 3.1, an exhaustive search was carried out to

choose the optimal threshold value. The reduction of the threshold value reduces the noise detected as FVs steadily, until the value 10 is reached. As this value decreases, more and more true FVs start to be lost, so 10 was selected as the optimal thresholding value. To exemplify this, Table 3 specifies 4 intermediate values in this range, including the optimal value 10. It can be seen that as the threshold value decreases, the correlation between the percentage of change in the flow voids area and patient recovery increases. On the other hand, the Student's t-test showed no significant differences in the area of the FVs obtained ($p < 0.05$) for the set of images taken seconds apart for any of the different threshold values tested. This suggests that our baseline approach is robust and consistent, obtaining repeatable results over the time. To qualitatively compare the effect of the threshold value, several examples of binary masks obtained using different threshold values are shown below. Specifically, Fig. 8 shows the binary masks obtained using our baseline approach, where the FVs are marked in white. It can be seen how the reduction of the threshold value decreases the noise present in the image while keeping the FVs really significant.

Finally, to evaluate the evolution of the FVs changes, representative examples of pre and post-treatment image pairs are shown in Fig. 9 together with the segmentation masks obtained by our baseline approach. Based on all shown, we can conclude that our baseline approach succeeds in extracting the FVs from the images in an accurate and robust manner. We see how this is true both in the images obtained before and after treatment, which allows us to compare the area of the FVs in an efficient way.

4.2. Robust quantitative analysis of the evolution of the FVs changes using unsupervised image deformable registration: robust approach

In this section we show the results obtained using our robust approach. Our robust approach is based on the use of a neural network to perform a deformable registration to equalize the noise and differences due to deformations of both images. Once both images are aligned, the segmentation is performed and the percentage of change of the FVs area is calculated. All the results involving the training of the network and the registration of the images are shown below. Fig. 10 shows the evolution of the training and validation of the neural network for CC OCTA image deformable registration. It can be seen that the training has been successful, with the network reaching convergence.

The performance in test is shown in Table 4, where we can see the different values obtained by comparing the CC OCTA images before and after registration for the different image similarity metrics. As can be

Fig. 8. Examples showing the result of applying the proposed baseline approach using different threshold values.

Fig. 9. Representative pairs of CC OCTA images obtained before and after treatment. Each image is accompanied by a segmentation mask obtained using our baseline approach where the FVs are shown in white.

seen, all the similarity metrics indicate that after applying our registration network both images are much more similar to each other. This increase in similarity occurs thanks to the correction of all the small deformations suffered by these rough and granular images. In particular, our method shows a suitable performance, providing a value of 0.7243 for the SSIM, a 0.7109 for the MSSIM, a 0.1704 for the VIF, a 469.0 for the MSE and a 0.1801 for the NRMSE. The proposed deformable registration method performs satisfactorily, demonstrating that our model exhibits significant generalization capability with excellent, robust and stable registration performance.

Complementarily, Fig. 11 shows the illustrative results of applying the registration network to different pairs of pre-treatment and post-treatment images. In particular, column one shows the pre-treatment image, column two the post-treatment image and column three the pixel-to-pixel differences between the pre-treatment and post-treatment images with a color code where red represents a darker value (more FVs)

in the pre-treatment image, blue a darker value in the post-treatment image and white the same value in the two images. Two values whose intensity value is separated by less than 10 units are counted as equal because they are not representative. This visualization is clear and intuitive and helps to see at a glance how the distribution of the FVs has changed in our CC OCTA image aiding in treatment monitoring. As we can see, our network manages to mitigate the noise produced by the multiple deformations and misalignments of the images while maintaining the really significant differences without producing strange and undesired deformations.

Although the obtained results show that our neural network is able to perform an efficient image registration, eliminating noise while keeping the FVs that represent really significant differences, we must check if its application helps to obtain a more accurate and robust biomarker. For this, we show below the results obtained using our robust approach as we did for our baseline approximation in Section 4.1. The correlation

Fig. 10. Evolution of the training loss in red and the validation loss in blue throughout 550 epochs.

Table 4
Different metrics showing the performance of the deformable registration in terms of image similarity.

Methods	SSIM ↑	MSSIM ↑	VIF ↑	MSE ↓	NRMSE ↓
Before registration	0.0931	0.2103	0.0394	1482.1	0.3180
After registration	0.7243	0.7109	0.1704	469.0	0.1801

obtained between the percentage of change in FVs area and patient recovery using our robust approach was 0.5016. Our robust approach is, therefore, able to extract this biomarker more effectively than our baseline approach. On the other hand, the Student’s t-test showed no significant difference ($p = 0.001$) in the area of the FVs obtained using this approach. This demonstrates that our approach using the registration neural network is robust and allows the calculation of the FVs area for each image in a repeatable manner.

Fig. 12 shows representative examples of pre and post-processing image pairs along with the segmentation masks obtained using our robust approach. We can observe how in comparison to the images obtained using our baseline approach, the segmentation masks present a smaller number of more accurately detected FVs. This is due to the fact that the registration application corrects small texture deformations existing between both images that were segmented as FVs although they were noise. As the images are much better aligned, the segmentation masks are much more accurate, which allows the calculation of the percentage of change in the FVs area between them to be much more precise and robust.

4.3. Comparison with the state of the art

As mentioned above, the Phansalkar et al. (2011) is the most widely used method in clinical studies for FVs segmentation in CC OCTA images (although it was designed to segment cell nuclei in cytological and histological images). Consequently, this segmentation method was chosen to compare and validate our proposals. In Table 5, we can observe the correlation coefficient obtained between the percentage of change in FVs area calculated by each of the approaches and the patient recovery. We can see how this coefficient is much higher when we use our baseline approach than when we use the state of the art. This implies that our baseline methodology alone is able to extract the biomarker in a

Fig. 11. Result of applying the registration network to different pairs of pre-treatment and post-treatment images.

Fig. 12. Representative pairs of CC OCTA images and their FVs predictions that was obtained by the proposed segmentation approach with pre-registered images. Each pair represents the response to photodynamic therapy in the treatment of patients with chronic CSC.

Table 5

Comparison of the correlation coefficient obtained using the state of the art, our baseline approach and our robust approach.

	State of the art (Phansalkar et al., 2011)	Baseline Approach	Robust Approach
Coefficient	0.2649	0.4850	0.5016
p-value	0.009	0.001	0.001

more accurate and robust way, allowing us to make predictions and comparisons in a more accurate and efficient way. At the same time, as previously mentioned, our robust approach outperforms our baseline approach by correcting for the deformations and noise present between images obtained at different time instants of the treatment.

Complementarily, Fig. 13 shows the binary masks obtained using the state of the art, our baseline approach and our robust approach. In

accordance with the correlation results, we can observe how our approaches obtain a more accurate segmentation and with less noise than the state of the art proposal. Likewise, we observe how our robust approach outperforms our baseline approach, obtaining fewer false positives that affect when calculating the increase or decrease of the number of FVs between CC OCTA images.

Finally, in Fig. 14, we can see a summary of the results obtained in the class separability analysis. In particular, this analysis shows the different recovered and non-recovered patients grouped into 21 value ranges for easy viewing. As we can see, the obtained results reinforce the previous results. The use of our baseline approach increases the separability between the recovered and non-recovered patient classes with respect to the state of the art. We can observe how there is less crossover between both classes and how the range between this percentage of change in the FVs area between them is widened.

Specifically, the state of the art covers a range of -0.2187%

Fig. 13. Representative pairs of CC OCTA images obtained before and after laser treatment and the FVs segmentation masks obtained using the state of the art and the two proposed approaches.

decrease in the FVs area, up to a 0.5313 increase, while our baseline approach ranges from -0.5682 to 6.5718 . In the same way, our robust approach achieves better class separability than our baseline approach, with a total range from -1.6931 to 46.9069 .

From the obtained results, we can conclude that both (our baseline approach and our robust approach) overcome the state of the art in FVs segmentation using CC OCTA images. Our robust approach, through the use of a neural network, allows correcting the deformations that are formed when obtaining images at quite separated time instants (from days to months).

This deformable registration achieves an accurate and robust result, despite all the problematic characteristics of CC OCTA images. This allows us to quantify changes in FVs distribution in a more robust and accurate manner, increasing its efficacy as a biomarker, which improves the treatment and pathology monitoring. Although in our robust approach we have used our deformable registration network as a previous step to the proposed segmentation methodology, we would like to

highlight that this neural network can be used in a complementary way with other segmentation proposals as it is used with ours, making this a versatile methodology and adaptable to other algorithms. In our specific case we have demonstrated the efficacy of our approaches by monitoring the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy in patients with chronic CSC. This gives our methodologies a great potential for clinical use, to be used both in the case presented and in other real clinical scenarios, being its use extensible to other pathologies or treatments associated with this type of imaging. In addition, our proposals have great potential for application in other imaging modalities with similar characteristics and challenges. Specifically, OCTA imaging of other capillary plexuses also of great complexity and clinical interest for the detection of biomarkers for the monitoring of different ocular diseases.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we have described both the great clinical potential, as

Fig. 14. Distribution of classes of recovered and non-recovered patients in the different ranges of values obtained using the state of the art, our baseline approach and our robust approach.

well as the main challenges of the FVs quantification in CC OCTA images, an emerging ophthalmic imaging technology with great potential to support early diagnosis of relevant ocular and systemic diseases. These challenges arise from the rough and granular texture, multiple complex deformations and the landmark scarcity that characterize this type of imaging and greatly affect the use of FVs distribution as a biomarker.

Taking into account the problems mentioned above, as well as the large gap in the literature on this topic, we have proposed two fully automatic approaches to quantify changes in the FVs distribution using CC OCTA images. To do this, we first designed a complete methodology for the FVs segmentation based on the use of local contrast enhancement followed by a global thresholding strategy. Second, a robust approach, which deals with the limitations of the first approach by solving the deformations and differences due to the different time instant in which the images are acquired. To do so, in this second approach, a neural network is proposed that is trained in an unsupervised manner to perform a deformable registration. Our network succeeds in aligning the inconsistencies present between the two images despite the landmark scarcity and the complex deformations that characterize this imaging modality. Both approaches have proven to be more accurate and robust in quantifying changes in FVs distribution than the state of the art commonly applied in the clinical setting, improving the efficacy of FVs distribution as a biomarker.

In this regard, the proposed approaches were tested with cases from a real clinical study on monitoring the response to photodynamic therapy treatment of patients diagnosed with chronic CSC, a pathological condition in which fluid accumulates under the retina, causing serous detachment and vision loss. Although the two proposed approaches to measure the evolution of FVs changes were validated using images from patients with this pathology, their use is extensible to other clinical cases using this imaging modality or imaging modalities with similar characteristics.

Finally, it is worth mentioning the limitation of not being able to establish a ground truth in this type of imaging. This limitation implies evaluating the efficacy of the method through other mechanisms, as in our case is to increase the correlation and separability of the target classes. Although this evaluation is a reasonable approximation, it is limited, so these methods should be tested with other datasets and other targets. In addition, we recall that exist a problem in distinguishing between flow voids that are due to tissue hypofusion and those that are caused by some deformation in the upper layers of the choroid. The resolution of this problem is of great interest and can be addressed at the time of image capture, which represent an important future work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Emilio López-Varela: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Joaquim de Moura:** Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **José Ignacio Fernández-Vigo:** Validation, Investigation, Data acquisition, Supervision, Project administration. **Francisco Javier Moreno-Morillo:** Validation, Investigation, Data acquisition, Supervision, Project administration. **Jorge Novo:** Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Marcos Ortega:** Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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